

Supplementary Document for STD2Vformer

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APPENDIX I DATASETS

We conducted experiments on seven publicly available real-world datasets, including four traffic datasets (METR-LA, PEMS-BAY, PEMS04, PEMS08), one illness surveillance dataset (TaiWan-ILL), one electricity consumption dataset (NL-Electricity), and one air quality dataset (Beijing-AirQuality). Table A-1 provides a summary of the statistics for these datasets. Next, we will introduce the Traffic Dataset, the Illness Dataset, Electricity Consumption Dataset, and the air quality dataset separately. We will discuss how the datasets were collected, structured, preprocessed, and segmented to train the models.

A. Traffic Dataset

We first introduce four traffic datasets. Two datasets capture traffic speed information, while the other two focus on traffic flow. Specifically, the traffic speed dataset records the average speed of vehicles in miles per hour. Considering the imposed speed limits in these areas, the speed data typically consists of floating-point values, usually below 70. On the other hand, the traffic flow dataset represents the number of vehicles passing through and are integer values, reaching up to a few hundred.

All the raw data are collected from sensors that take measurements every 30 seconds, aggregating them into 5-minute intervals. For the METR-LA and PEMS-BAY datasets, we follow the preprocessing techniques described in DCRNN [1]. The datasets are normalized using the standard normalization method. We divide the datasets into three subsets: training, validation, and test sets, with a ratio of 7:1:2. We compute the pairwise road network distances between sensors and build the adjacency matrix using a thresholded Gaussian kernel, following DCRNN [1].

Regarding the PEMS04 and PEMS08 datasets, we apply the preprocessing techniques described in PDFormer [2]. These datasets are normalized using the min-max normalization method. We split them into training, validation, and test sets using a 6:2:2 ratio. We use the traffic network provided by PDFormer [2], where redundant detectors are removed to ensure a distance of over 3.5 miles between adjacent detectors, creating a more streamlined network.

B. ILI Rate Dataset

The ILI Rate dataset comprises ILI surveillance data, encompassing ILI cases at the county/city level sourced from the Centers for Disease Control, Taiwan province, China (Taiwan

CDC), and has been publicly available on a weekly basis since 2008. Additionally, Taiwan's geographical characteristics make it an interesting case for this research. The main island of Taiwan is surrounded by the sea, which minimizes the influence of cross-border land transportation on the spread of diseases. The island's scattered counties/cities can each be regarded as a node, and the hubs of maritime and aerial transportation are primarily some key nodal cities. This distribution characteristic is a typical representation of the clustering of developed-underdeveloped urban areas in most regions. Such generality assures the generalization capability of functional topological information in influenza transmission.

The dataset covers 12 years, from week 14, 2008, to week 10, 2020, spanning from the initiation of ILI reporting in Taiwan (19 counties/cities of the main island) to the commencement of control measures against COVID-19.

We downloaded weekly ILI data at the county/city level from the Taiwan CDC website¹. Additionally, to establish a geographical adjacency matrix, we computed the straight-line distance on the Earth's surface based on the latitude and longitude of each county/city. If the distance was less than 60km, we considered the county/city pair to be geographically adjacent [3]. Subsequently, we aggregated ILI case counts across various age groups and total emergency department visits. The ILI Rate was then calculated using the following formula:

$$ILI\ Rate_{t,k} = \frac{N_{t,k}^{ILI}}{N_{t,k}^{vist}} \quad (1)$$

where t represents the week number, k represents the county/city; $N_{t,k}^{ILI}$ and $N_{t,k}^{vist}$ denote the total count of ILI-diagnosed patients and the total count of outpatient and inpatient visits within county/city k during week t , respectively. When processing the ILI datasets, we adhere to the reprocessing techniques outlined in [3]. Specifically, the datasets are normalized using standard normalization methods. Subsequently, we partition them into training, validation, and test sets following a 6:2:2 ratio.

C. Electricity Consumption Dataset

The Electricity Consumption Dataset is derived from the Netherlands Smart Meter Data², which provides hourly measurements from 80 user-consented smart meters spanning May 1, 2012 to March 7, 2014. As the data originates from real-world measurements, missing values are frequent. To mitigate their impact, we removed two periods with excessive missing

¹<https://data.cdc.gov.tw/en/dataset/hi-outpatient-emergency-visit-influenza-like-illness>

²<https://www.liander.nl/partners/datadiensten/open-data/data>

TABLE A-1
STATISTICS OF DATASETS

Type	Dataset	Node	Edges	Time Step	Time Range
Traffic Flow	PEMS04	307	680	16992	Jan 1st 2018 to Feb 28th 2018
	PEMS08	170	548	17856	July 1st 2018 to Aug 31th 2018
Traffic Speed	METR-LA	207	1722	34272	Mar 1st 2012 to Jun 30th 2012
	PEMS-BAY	325	2694	52116	Jan 1st 2017 to May 31th 2017
Electricity Consumption	NL-Electricity	78	N/A	8760	Jan 1st 2013 to Dec 31th 2013
ILI Rate	TaiWan-ILI	19	68	574	Week 14 2008 to Week 10 2020
Air Quality	Beijing-AirQuality	30	N/A	8701	Jan 1st 2017 to Jan 31th 2018

entries and selected the interval from January 1, 2013 to December 31, 2013 for our experiments. The dataset was obtained from Hugging Face³. Following the setup in [4] and considering the dataset’s characteristics, we partitioned it into training, validation, and test sets with a ratio of 6:2:2. Furthermore, min-max normalization was applied to rescale the data into the range $(-1, 1)$. Since no adjacency matrix is provided, this dataset corresponds to a graph-free spatiotemporal forecasting task.

D. Air Quality Dataset

The Air Quality dataset is derived from the Beijing City⁴, which provides hourly air quality measurements from 30 stations spanning from January 1, 2017, to January 31, 2018. As the data originates from real-world observations, missing values occur frequently. To better simulate real-world industrial scenarios, we replace all missing values with zeros rather than applying any imputation methods. The dataset is publicly available on GitHub⁵. Considering the characteristics of this dataset, we divide it into training, validation, and test sets with a ratio of 6:2:2. Furthermore, min-max normalization was applied to rescale the data into the range $(-1, 1)$. Since no adjacency matrix is provided, this dataset corresponds to a graph-free spatiotemporal forecasting task.

APPENDIX II BASELINES

We introduce the details about baselines as follows:

- STGCN [5] constructs multiple local Spatiotemporal graphs to capture Spatiotemporal correlations synchronously.
- Gwnet [6] superimposes gated TCNs and GCNs layer by layer to jointly capture spatial and temporal dependencies.
- AGCRN [7] augments traditional graph convolution with adaptive graph generation and node adaptive parameter learning and integrates it into recurrent neural networks.
- STTN [8] leverages spatial attention to capture spatial dependencies and temporal attention to capture long-term temporal correlations.

- GMAN [9] is an attention-based model that superimposes spatial, temporal, and transformational attention.
- STID [10] adds node and temporal embeddings to the original input sequence and utilizes FC networks for prediction.
- ST-Norm [11] proposes spatial and temporal normalization modules for joint use with WaveNet.
- D2STGNN [12] innovatively decouples diffusion and inherent traffic signals to enhance Spatiotemporal modeling in traffic forecasting.
- PDFormer [2] incorporates a spatial self-attention module to capture dynamic spatial dependencies. Additionally, it utilizes a traffic delay-aware feature transformation module to accurately model the time delay associated with spatial information propagation.
- AFDGCN [13] introduces a dynamic graph convolution network with attention fusion to jointly model multi-scale Spatiotemporal dependencies through enhanced temporal interactions and a dynamic graph learner combined with GRU.
- MegaCRN [14] employs a meta-graph learner for Spatiotemporal meta-graph learning.
- STIDGCN [15] proposes an interactive learning framework composed of spatial and temporal modules for downsampling traffic data.
- PGCN [16] introduces a novel approach that progressively adapts graph structures to online input data during both training and testing phases.
- PMC-GCN [17] uses a personalized enhanced GCN with a trainable diagonal matrix and multi-head self-attention to improve robustness in prediction.
- TESTAM [18] innovatively employs a mixture-of-experts model with three specialized experts to effectively capture both recurring and non-recurring traffic patterns through enhanced spatiotemporal attention and dynamic graph modeling.
- DG2RNN [19] introduces a Dual Graph Convolution Module to capture local spatial dependencies through road distance and adaptive correlation. It employs a Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Layer and a temporal attention mechanism for dynamic temporal dependencies and a spatial attention mechanism for global spatial dependencies, enhancing traffic flow prediction.

³<https://huggingface.co/datasets/OpenSynth/TUDelft-Electricity-Consumption-1.0>

⁴<http://www.geodata.cn>

⁵<https://github.com/ZebornDuan/KDDCup2018>

Fig. A-1. The impact of the selected number of neighbors (K) in METR-LA, with the green dashed line indicating the minimum prediction error.

Fig. A-2. Impact of the number of frequency components (O) in METR-LA, with the green dashed line indicating the minimum prediction error.

Fig. A-3. The impact of the selected number of neighbors (K) in PEMS08, with the green dashed line indicating the minimum prediction error.

Fig. A-4. Impact of the number of frequency components (O) in PEMS08, with the green dashed line indicating the minimum prediction error.

APPENDIX III PARAMETER SENSITIVITY

In the following, we investigate the sensitivity of STD2Vformer to two key hyperparameters: the number of selected neighbors (K) and the number of frequency components (O). Figures A-1 and A-2 present the results on the METR-LA dataset for 15-minute forecasting ($F = 3$), while Figures A-3 and A-4 report the corresponding results on the PEMS08 dataset.

From Figures A-1 and A-3, we observe that the optimal number of neighbors is approximately $K = 9$ for METR-LA and $K = 6$ for PEMS08. These values are well aligned with our heuristic selection rule $K = \max(3, \lceil 0.04N \rceil)$, validating the rationality of this design choice. As shown in Figures A-2 and A-4, the best performance is achieved when the number of frequency components is set to $O = 64$. For MAE and MAPE, and for most RMSE cases, a consistent trend is observed: increasing K or O initially leads to a reduction in prediction error, as a larger neighborhood size or a richer frequency representation enhances the model capacity. However, when K or O exceeds a certain threshold, the prediction error begins to increase. This degradation can be attributed to the introduction of excessive noise and redundant information at larger K or

O values, which adversely affects the model’s generalization ability.

APPENDIX IV FIXED-HORIZON PREDICTION

In this section, we present additional experimental results of the proposed STD2Vformer on several benchmark datasets. Detailed results are provided in Table A-2 (PEMS08, PEMS04, PEMS-BAY, and NL-Electricity), and Table A-3 (Taiwan-ILI and Beijing-AirQuality). Across different domains, prediction horizons, and evaluation metrics, STD2Vformer consistently achieves near-optimal performance. Notably, on datasets without adjacency matrices—NL-Electricity and Beijing-AirQuality—our model still performs competitively, demonstrating strong robustness and generalization capability.

It is important to highlight that, to better reflect real-world industrial scenarios, we applied different missing-value handling strategies to the two real industrial datasets. For NL-Electricity, where the missing rate is approximately 2.5%, linear interpolation was used for imputation. For Beijing-AirQuality, which contains a higher missing rate of about 6.49%, we intentionally filled missing values with zero to

TABLE A-2

FIXED-HORIZON PREDICTION ON THE PEMS08, PEMS04 AND PEMS-BAY (WITH INPUT SEQUENCE LENGTH OF 60 MINUTES) DATASETS, AND NL-ELECTRICITY (WITH INPUT SEQUENCE LENGTH OF 12 HOURS). A LOWER MAE, RMSE, OR MAPE INDICATES A BETTER PREDICTION. THE BEST RESULTS ARE HIGHLIGHTED IN **BOLD**, AND THE SECOND BEST RESULTS ARE HIGHLIGHTED WITH A UNDERLINE.

Dataset	Model	15 minutes			30 minutes			60 minutes		
		MAE	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
PEMS08	Gwnet	15.88	28.81	5.34%	18.32	34.53	5.94%	21.17	41.78	7.39%
	AGCRN	16.27	29.47	5.85%	18.55	35.25	6.34%	21.32	42.23	7.24%
	STTN	15.89	28.76	5.51%	18.36	34.94	6.15%	20.87	41.15	6.93%
	STID	15.39	28.33	5.27%	17.89	34.57	6.11%	19.89	<u>40.56</u>	6.61%
	PDFformer	16.86	29.85	5.89%	18.16	34.81	6.09%	21.63	42.12	7.24%
	GMAN	16.32	30.18	5.64%	18.59	36.21	6.25%	21.52	43.40	7.17%
	ST-Norm	15.70	28.86	5.29%	18.38	35.11	6.39%	21.11	42.68	7.18%
	D2STGNN	15.56	28.31	5.26%	17.76	34.51	<u>5.84%</u>	20.38	40.42	6.78%
	STIDGCN	<u>15.31</u>	<u>28.23</u>	<u>5.14%</u>	<u>17.64</u>	<u>34.22</u>	5.98%	<u>19.92</u>	40.63	6.75%
	STGCN	18.13	30.85	6.30%	20.32	36.14	7.56%	22.95	43.95	7.97%
	AFDGCN	39.84	63.27	16.24%	36.95	62.89	14.86%	40.30	68.50	15.80%
	MegaCRN	16.57	29.44	5.64%	19.33	35.38	6.53%	30.48	50.56	12.37%
	PGCN	15.77	28.64	5.37%	17.97	34.61	6.02%	20.81	41.35	6.86%
	PMC-GCN	15.96	28.99	5.51%	18.38	34.73	6.19%	22.09	42.53	7.57%
	TESTAM	29.68	43.24	15.77%	23.15	42.22	8.74%	30.82	50.12	12.77%
	DG2RNN	16.07	29.69	5.41%	18.26	35.55	6.10%	21.22	42.46	7.14%
STD2Vformer	14.85	28.15	4.88%	17.20	34.19	5.67%	20.35	41.89	<u>6.70%</u>	
PEMS04	Gwnet	15.17	28.32	6.71%	17.15	32.73	7.43%	19.84	38.28	8.86%
	AGCRN	15.64	28.64	7.17%	17.72	33.43	8.10%	20.10	38.74	9.14%
	STTN	15.49	28.49	6.84%	17.58	33.02	7.80%	20.35	39.26	9.21%
	STID	<u>15.04</u>	<u>27.99</u>	<u>6.60%</u>	16.99	32.34	7.54%	19.57	<u>37.61</u>	8.90%
	PDFformer	15.62	28.64	7.09%	17.38	33.12	7.60%	19.97	38.83	8.95%
	GMAN	16.09	29.67	7.07%	17.88	34.62	7.75%	20.08	38.62	9.18%
	ST-Norm	15.44	28.52	6.82%	17.38	33.05	7.73%	19.85	38.05	8.81%
	D2STGNN	15.12	28.07	6.73%	17.10	32.72	7.64%	19.40	38.06	8.78%
	STIDGCN	15.11	28.00	6.79%	<u>16.72</u>	<u>32.23</u>	<u>7.21%</u>	19.11	37.31	<u>8.31%</u>
	STGCN	17.47	30.02	9.11%	18.45	34.34	8.24%	22.00	40.82	9.98%
	AFDGCN	36.42	60.10	19.13%	36.89	61.05	19.43%	40.60	65.95	22.15%
	MegaCRN	18.64	30.75	11.31%	27.13	41.55	17.79%	32.74	49.95	23.26%
	PGCN	15.22	28.43	6.66%	17.27	33.00	7.46%	19.77	38.32	8.69%
	PMC-GCN	15.62	29.02	6.90%	18.01	34.04	8.03%	20.88	40.10	9.30%
	TESTAM	20.23	35.81	10.68%	23.44	40.31	11.70%	30.04	46.83	20.77%
	DG2RNN	15.90	29.68	6.96%	17.77	33.92	7.74%	20.35	39.72	9.00%
STD2Vformer	14.71	27.51	6.29%	16.70	32.01	7.09%	19.83	39.59	8.30%	
PEMS-BAY	Gwnet	<u>1.13</u>	<u>2.27</u>	2.05%	1.39	2.93	2.59%	<u>1.68</u>	<u>3.61</u>	3.23%
	AGCRN	1.17	2.34	2.12%	1.45	3.05	2.72%	1.75	3.77	3.42%
	STTN	1.14	2.28	2.06%	1.43	2.99	2.67%	1.80	3.83	3.51%
	STID	1.23	2.39	2.26%	1.48	3.07	2.75%	1.70	3.66	4.61%
	PDFformer	1.14	2.30	2.05%	1.43	3.00	2.70%	1.74	3.78	3.43%
	GMAN	1.16	2.32	2.09%	1.43	3.00	2.64%	1.77	3.75	3.70%
	ST-Norm	1.15	2.30	2.10%	1.41	2.97	2.63%	1.74	3.72	3.41%
	D2STGNN	<u>1.13</u>	2.28	2.04%	<u>1.38</u>	2.91	2.58%	1.74	3.68	3.45%
	STIDGCN	<u>1.13</u>	<u>2.27</u>	2.03%	<u>1.38</u>	2.93	<u>2.56%</u>	1.66	3.57	3.36%
	AFDGCN	1.82	3.28	3.31%	2.09	3.90	3.90%	2.58	4.86	4.89%
	DCRNN	5.45	9.44	11.54%	5.17	9.52	11.28%	5.57	9.52	11.72%
	MegaCRN	1.12	2.28	2.07%	1.38	<u>2.92</u>	<u>2.58%</u>	1.76	3.82	3.44%
	PGCN	1.14	2.30	2.05%	1.41	2.98	2.63%	1.72	3.69	<u>3.29%</u>
	PMC-GCN	1.16	2.34	2.10%	1.49	3.12	2.80%	2.35	4.92	4.77%
	TESTAM	1.19	2.40	2.18%	1.53	3.20	2.86%	1.83	3.84	3.46%
	DG2RNN	1.62	3.38	3.03%	1.84	3.84	3.51%	2.13	4.41	4.17%
STD2Vformer	1.12	2.26	2.03%	1.36	3.09	2.54%	1.77	3.97	3.43%	
NL-Electricity	Gwnet	0.1556	0.2433	69.05%	0.1733	0.2654	76.02%	0.1753	<u>0.2620</u>	81.42%
	AGCRN	0.1434	0.2401	58.38%	0.1674	0.2527	77.84%	0.1755	0.2627	81.18%
	STTN	N/A								
	STID	0.1489	0.2467	60.27%	<u>0.1552</u>	0.2489	66.23%	0.1776	0.2736	77.09%
	PDFformer	N/A								
	GMAN	N/A								
	ST-Norm	0.1407	<u>0.2317</u>	58.51%	0.1554	<u>0.2432</u>	67.79%	0.1734	0.2668	74.89%
	D2STGNN	N/A								
	STIDGCN	<u>0.1384</u>	0.2293	57.85%	0.1553	0.2422	69.37%	<u>0.1717</u>	0.2544	76.04%
	STGCN	N/A								
	AFDGCN	N/A								
	MegaCRN	0.1535	0.2545	57.51%	0.1635	0.2783	<u>52.29%</u>	0.2033	0.3249	<u>67.90%</u>
	PGCN	N/A								
	PMC-GCN	N/A								
	TESTAM	0.2060	0.3596	<u>46.45%</u>	0.2131	0.3234	80.85%	0.2252	0.3403	84.27%
	DG2RNN	N/A								
STD2Vformer	0.1379	0.2616	42.48%	0.1547	0.2758	51.63%	0.1712	0.2973	55.98%	
NL-Electricity	Gwnet	0.1556	0.2433	69.05%	0.1733	0.2654	76.02%	0.1753	<u>0.2620</u>	81.42%
	AGCRN	0.1434	0.2401	58.38%	0.1674	0.2527	77.84%	0.1755	0.2627	81.18%
	STTN	N/A								
	STID	0.1489	0.2467	60.27%	<u>0.1552</u>	0.2489	66.23%	0.1776	0.2736	77.09%
	PDFformer	N/A								
	GMAN	N/A								
	ST-Norm	0.1407	<u>0.2317</u>	58.51%	0.1554	<u>0.2432</u>	67.79%	0.1734	0.2668	74.89%
	D2STGNN	N/A								
	STIDGCN	<u>0.1384</u>	0.2293	57.85%	0.1553	0.2422	69.37%	<u>0.1717</u>	0.2544	76.04%
	STGCN	N/A								
	AFDGCN	N/A								
	MegaCRN	0.1535	0.2545	57.51%	0.1635	0.2783	<u>52.29%</u>	0.2033	0.3249	<u>67.90%</u>
	PGCN	N/A								
	PMC-GCN	N/A								
	TESTAM	0.2060	0.3596	<u>46.45%</u>	0.2131	0.3234	80.85%	0.2252	0.3403	84.27%
	DG2RNN	N/A								
STD2Vformer	0.1379	0.2616	42.48%	0.1547	0.2758	51.63%	0.1712	0.2973	55.98%	

simulate a more challenging and extreme industrial setting. As shown in Table A-3, STD2Vformer achieves the best or

TABLE A-3
FIXED-HORIZON PREDICTION ON THE TAIWAN-ILI (WITH INPUT SEQUENCE LENGTH OF 52 WEEKS) AND BEIJING-AIRQUALITY DATASETS (WITH INPUT SEQUENCE LENGTH OF 24 HOURS). A LOWER MAE, RMSE, OR MAPE INDICATES A BETTER PREDICTION.

Dataset	Model	1 Week		
		MAE	RMSE	MAPE
Taiwan-ILI	Gwnet	0.0040	0.0054	31.31%
	AGCRN	0.0010	0.0014	7.75%
	STTN	0.0012	0.0018	8.52%
	STID	0.0012	0.0017	9.67%
	PDFformer	0.0011	0.0015	8.03%
	GMAN	0.0031	0.0044	22.84%
	ST-Norm	0.0043	0.0057	33.71%
	D2STGNN	0.0016	0.0019	14.37%
	STIDGCN	0.0011	0.0015	9.19%
	STGCN	0.0014	0.0018	12.45%
	AFDGCN	0.0052	0.0061	45.45%
	MegaCRN	0.0010	0.0014	8.22%
	PGCN	0.0039	0.0049	31.84%
	PMC-GCN	0.0012	0.0016	9.31%
	TESTAM	0.0014	0.0019	11.00%
	DG2RNN	0.0024	0.0031	22.09%
STD2Vformer	0.0009	0.0013	7.06%	
Dataset	Model	24 hours		
		MAE	RMSE	MAPE
Beijing-AirQuality	Gwnet	32.79	46.67	68.88%
	AGCRN	35.93	50.27	76.90%
	STTNS	N/A	N/A	N/A
	STID	28.61	42.10	61.49%
	PDFformer	N/A	N/A	N/A
	GMAN	N/A	N/A	N/A
	ST-Norm	31.37	45.15	64.17%
	D2STGNN	N/A	N/A	N/A
	STIDGCN	28.45	41.45	62.85%
	STGCN	N/A	N/A	N/A
	AFDGCN	N/A	N/A	N/A
	MegaCRN	30.49	45.04	61.95%
	PGCN	N/A	N/A	N/A
	PMC-GCN	N/A	N/A	N/A
	TESTAM	32.86	55.61	66.42%
	STD2Vformer	28.04	42.08	57.67%

near-best performance in almost all cases. Furthermore, as shown in Table A-4, the selected station results on the Beijing-AirQuality dataset indicate that STD2Vformer remains highly effective across different missing-value ratios, further validating its robustness.

APPENDIX V

INCREASING GAP LENGTH AND PREDICTION LENGTH

In the main text, we mentioned that the proposed STD2Vformer can theoretically generate prediction sequences of arbitrary lengths, starting from any point. In this section, we experimentally investigate the impact of increasing gap length and prediction length on the model’s predictive performance.

A. Increasing Gap length

Experimental Setup: To evaluate the performance of the proposed STD2Vformer with varying gap lengths, we conducted experiments using the METR-LA dataset. We selected STID as the baseline model for comparison, which helps provide a clearer understanding of the experimental results. In this experiment, both the input sequence length and prediction sequence length were fixed at 60 minutes, and the model was trained under a no-gap configuration.

In the experiment, STID rebuilds the model and retrains it from scratch for each different gap length. In contrast, STD2Vformer (w/ FT) fine-tunes a pre-trained model to accommodate various gap lengths. STD2Vformer (w/o FT) directly generates prediction sequences based on the target prediction horizon without fine-tuning, while STD2Vformer (w/ NB) does not require fine-tuning, but instead improves performance by incorporating non-blind meta-information. Non-blind meta-information refers to injecting prediction length-related and position-related data as input to the model (as shown in Fig. A-5). This design enables STD2Vformer to remain aware of the downstream prediction horizon during both training and inference, effectively narrowing the performance gap between the fine-tuned and non-fine-tuned settings.

Experimental Results: The results are presented in Table A-5. We observed that, even without fine-tuning, the proposed STD2Vformer (w/o FT) outperforms the retrained STID model. Specifically, compared to STD2Vformer (w/o FT), the average MAE for STID increased by 53.20%, with the largest increase reaching 96.24%. This demonstrates that STD2Vformer can maintain robust predictive performance even without fine-tuning. Moreover, when fine-tuning STD2Vformer or incorporating non-blind meta-information (w/ NB), we observed average improvements of 12.17% and 13.13%, respectively, over the STD2Vformer (w/o FT) for long-horizon predictions (gap length > 60 minutes). Additionally, as shown in Fig. A-6, we found that the prediction error of STD2Vformer increases linearly with the gap length, with a slope of approximately 0.0294.

Conclusion: Without fine-tuning, STD2Vformer outperforms the baseline model that requires retraining. Furthermore, fine-tuning the model or injecting non-blind meta-information (such as prediction horizon details) further enhances STD2Vformer’s prediction accuracy. As the gap length increases, the prediction error increases linearly. This allows us to predict the expected error for different gap lengths effectively, and when the predicted error exceeds a certain threshold, we can apply rapid fine-tuning to improve performance.

B. Increasing Prediction length

Experimental Setup: To assess the performance of the proposed STD2Vformer with increasing prediction lengths, we conducted experiments on the METR-LA dataset. For comparison and better understanding of the results, we chose STID as the baseline model. In this experiment, both the input and prediction sequence lengths were fixed at 60 minutes, and the model was trained without any gap.

In the experiment, STID rebuilds the model and retrains it from scratch for each different prediction horizon, while STD2Vformer (w/ FT) fine-tunes the pre-trained model for various target lengths. STD2Vformer (w/o FT) directly generates prediction sequences based on the target horizon without fine-tuning, whereas STD2Vformer (w/ NB) improves its performance by incorporating non-blind meta-information. Non-blind meta-information refers to injecting prediction horizon and position-related data into the model as input (as shown in Fig. A-5).

TABLE A-4

FIXED-HORIZON PREDICTION RESULTS ON THE BEIJING-AIRQUALITY DATASET (WITH INPUT SEQUENCE LENGTH OF 24 HOURS) ACROSS STATIONS WITH DIFFERENT MISSING-VALUE RATES. LOWER MAE, RMSE, AND MAPE INDICATE BETTER PERFORMANCE.

Dataset	Model	<5%			<10%			<20%			20+%		
		MAE	RMSE	MAPE									
Beijing-AirQuality	STID	17.69	26.81	38.82%	27.93	40.64	57.63%	30.95	45.5	61.27%	34.04	49.25	70.68%
	STIDGCN	18.56	27.65	38.82%	27.43	40.15	57.44%	30.9	44.43	65.10%	33.91	50.01	73.90%
	STD2Vformer	16.69	26.24	35.27%	26.56	39.71	52.55%	30.24	44.26	61.22%	33.86	48.15	69.75%

Fig. A-5. The overview of the overall architecture of the proposed STD2Vformer with the Non-Blind (NB) configuration.

TABLE A-5

RESULTS OF THE INCREASING GAP-LENGTH EXPERIMENT. THE IMPROVEMENT RATIOS ARE DEFINED AS $\text{Imp.}(\mathcal{S}) = \frac{\text{MAE}_{\text{BASE}} - \text{MAE}_{\mathcal{S}}}{\text{MAE}_{\text{BASE}}}$, WHERE $\mathcal{S} \in \{\text{w/ FT, w/ NB, STID}\}$ AND THE BASE CORRESPONDS TO STD2VFORMER (W/O FT).

Dataset	Pred Length (minutes)	Gap Length (minutes)	STD2Vformer (w/o FT)		STD2Vformer (w/ FT)		STD2Vformer (w/ NB)		STID (w/ FT)	
			MAE	MAE	Imp.	MAE	Imp.	MAE	Imp.	
METR-LA	60	60	8.58	8.41	1.93%	8.71	-1.57%	16.83	-96.24%	
		75	9.25	8.77	5.18%	8.90	3.77%	16.88	-82.46%	
		90	9.87	9.10	7.83%	9.08	8.04%	16.74	-69.58%	
		120	10.98	9.65	12.10%	9.44	14.02%	17.44	-58.83%	
		180	12.70	11.14	12.29%	10.29	18.91%	16.63	-31.00%	
		240	13.82	11.36	17.79%	11.30	18.20%	16.33	-18.22%	
		300	14.62	12.01	17.85%	12.30	15.83%	16.97	-16.08%	

TABLE A-6

RESULTS OF THE INCREASING PREDICTION-LENGTH EXPERIMENT. THE IMPROVEMENT RATIOS ARE COMPUTED AS $\text{Imp.}(\mathcal{S}) = \frac{\text{MAE}_{\text{BASE}} - \text{MAE}_{\mathcal{S}}}{\text{MAE}_{\text{BASE}}}$, WHERE $\mathcal{S} \in \{\text{w/ FT, w/ NB, STID}\}$ AND THE BASE CORRESPONDS TO STD2VFORMER (W/O FT).

Dataset	Gap Length (minutes)	Pred Length (minutes)	STD2Vformer (w/o FT)		STD2Vformer (w/ FT)		STD2Vformer (w/ NB)		STID (w/ FT)	
			MAE	MAE	Imp.	MAE	Imp.	MAE	Imp.	
METR-LA	0	60	5.05	5.39	-6.71%	5.32	-5.32%	5.43	-7.53%	
		75	5.74	5.97	-3.91%	5.88	-2.35%	6.07	-5.71%	
		90	6.17	6.40	-3.79%	6.70	0.15%	6.59	-6.93%	
		120	6.71	6.70	0.15%	6.94	-3.42%	7.61	-13.47%	
		180	8.03	8.00	0.37%	8.28	6.13%	8.57	-6.76%	
		240	9.40	9.06	3.59%	8.82	6.13%	8.98	4.45%	
		300	10.27	9.66	5.95%	9.50	7.46%	9.84	4.22%	

Experimental Results: As shown in Table A-6, STD2Vformer (w/o FT) achieves an average improvement of 4.54% in prediction accuracy over STID with retraining. Notably, STD2Vformer (w/o FT) outperforms the retrained STID model when the prediction length is under 180 minutes. However, as the prediction length extends to 240 and 300 minutes, the performance of STD2Vformer (w/o FT) drops below that of the retrained STID model. We attribute this decline to the distribution shift between the input

and output sequences during long-term predictions, which causes the learned mapping to break down. Nevertheless, by incorporating relevant time horizon information (w/ NB) or fine-tuning STD2Vformer, we can reduce prediction errors, bringing long-term prediction performance closer to or even surpassing that of retrained STID. As shown in Figure A-7, we also observe that the MAE of STD2Vformer increases linearly with the prediction length, with a slope of 0.0213.

Conclusion: In experiments with increasing prediction

Fig. A-6. MAE Results of the Increasing Gap Length Experiment. "Fit" refers to the trend line of STD2Vformer's MAE increase as the gap length grows, obtained through least squares fitting. The numerical results are shown in Table A-5.

Fig. A-7. MAE results of the Increasing Prediction Length Experiment. "Fit" refers to the trend line of STD2Vformer's MAE increase as the prediction length grows, obtained through least squares fitting. The numerical results are shown in Table A-6.

lengths, STD2Vformer outperforms the baseline model in most cases. Its prediction error exhibits a linear relationship with the prediction length, enabling us to effectively predict the expected error for varying prediction lengths. When prediction errors exceed a certain threshold, we can apply rapid fine-tuning to enhance performance. We believe the primary limitation of STD2Vformer stems from temporal heterogeneity, which is caused by the distribution shift between input and output sequences in long-term predictions. To address this issue, future work will integrate techniques such as Continual Learning (CL) to improve long-term prediction accuracy.

APPENDIX VI EFFICIENCY STUDY

In this section, we present the Efficiency experiment results on the METR-LA dataset and a more complex dataset, PEMS04, under prediction lengths $F = 3, 6, 12$, see Fig. A-8 and Fig. A-9. As shown, across all prediction lengths on both datasets, our proposed STD2Vformer consistently achieves the best overall performance in terms of prediction accuracy, inference time, and peak training memory consumption. These results demonstrate that STD2Vformer not only delivers high accuracy but also exhibits superior computational efficiency.

APPENDIX VII DECOMPOSITION STRATEGIES ANALYSIS

In this section, we conduct a systematic comparison between the proposed Date2Vec decomposition and established time-series decomposition methods. We further evaluate their performance under noisy conditions to assess robustness in realistic environments.

A. Comparative Analysis of Decomposition Strategies

To substantiate the superiority of our proposed Date2Vec module, we compared it against two well-established time-series decomposition mechanisms widely used in recent state-of-the-art models:

- **Series Decomposition (w/ Decomp. in [20]):** The decomposition block proposed in Autoformer [20].
- **MOE Decomposition (w/ Decomp. in [21]):** The mixture-of-experts decomposition strategy adopted by Fedformer [21] and TDformer [22].

The comparative results are reported in Table A-7. Empirical results show that replacing the proposed Date2Vec module with mature time-series decomposition techniques consistently leads to performance degradation. This performance gap mainly stems from the fact that most existing decomposition methods rely on predefined fixed kernel sizes, which inherently limit their receptive fields and hinder their ability to capture long-term temporal trends. In contrast, the proposed Date2Vec module is grounded in Fourier analysis, enabling a global decomposition of time-series signals without relying on local kernel assumptions. As a result, Date2Vec can more effectively model long-range temporal structures and complex periodic patterns, which are critical for the target forecasting task.

TABLE A-7
ABLATION STUDY ON METR-LA. THE BEST RESULTS ARE HIGHLIGHTED IN **BOLD**.

Dataset	Model	15 minutes			30 minutes			60 minutes		
		MAE	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
	STD2Vformer	3.26	8.07	15.59%	4.04	9.61	23.32%	5.05	11.52	32.79%
METR-LA	w/ Decomp. in [20]	3.50	8.22	19.86%	4.27	9.88	26.81%	5.73	12.02	44.15%
	w/ Decomp. in [21]	3.30	8.17	16.63%	4.13	9.86	26.20%	5.34	12.16	38.75%

B. Robustness Analysis Against Input Noise

To assess the stability of STD2Vformer under real-world conditions where data quality may be degraded, we conduct a robustness analysis by injecting Gaussian noise into the input signals. Noise generation follows the official implementation of the Time-Series-Library⁶.

Figure A-10 reports the MAE of 15-minute forecasts on the METR-LA dataset under increasing noise levels. As shown, STD2Vformer consistently outperforms its variants using alternative decomposition strategies (Series Decomposition and MOE Decomposition) as well as the strong baseline STID across all noise intensities. These results demonstrate that the proposed learning-based decomposition method exhibits superior robustness to noise perturbations.

⁶<https://github.com/thuml/Time-Series-Library>

Fig. A-8. Efficiency comparison on METR-LA at different horizons.

Fig. A-9. Efficiency comparison on PEMS04 at different horizons.

Fig. A-10. Robustness analysis showing MAE performance under different levels of injected Gaussian noise. The results correspond to 15-minute prediction horizons on the METR-LA dataset. Our model (STD2Vformer) demonstrates superior stability compared to baselines.

We attribute this robustness to the spectral characteristics of real-world noise and the design of our Date2Vec module. In practice, noise typically appears as high-frequency, low-amplitude fluctuations. STD2Vformer explicitly learns only the $(K + 1)$ dominant frequency components in Ω_S , which effectively acts as a low-pass spectral filter. This mechanism suppresses high-frequency noise while preserving dominant temporal patterns, leading to stable trends and periodic rep-

resentations. Consequently, the model avoids overfitting to spurious local variations and maintains reliable predictive performance even under severe noise interference.

APPENDIX VIII BATCH SIZE ADAPTABILITY

In this section, we evaluate STD2Vformer under different batch sizes in terms of MAE, inference time (s/iter), and throughput (samples/s), where throughput is computed as Batch Size/Time. All experiments in this section are conducted on an NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU. These experiments are designed to demonstrate the practicality of STD2Vformer for deployment on edge devices. From the table, we can observe that our method works reliably across different batch sizes and exhibits relatively stable performance. Moreover, as the batch size increases, the algorithm's throughput grows in an approximately linear manner. This suggests that our method is highly adaptable to varying batch sizes during the inference phase.

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TABLE A-8
PERFORMANCE UNDER DIFFERENT BATCH SIZES ON THE METR-LA
AND PEMS08 DATASETS FOR A 15-MINUTE FORECASTING HORIZON.

Dataset	Batch Size	MAE	Time (s/iter)	Throughput (sample/s)
METR-LA	8	3.24	0.1312	60.99
	16	3.24	0.1587	100.80
	32	3.26	0.1192	268.44
	64	3.27	0.1017	629.18
	128	3.29	0.1094	1170.20
	<i>Mean ± Std.</i>	3.26 ± 0.02	0.1240 ± 0.0200	-
PEMS08	8	14.51	0.1156	69.21
	16	14.64	0.1446	110.61
	32	14.79	0.1411	226.79
	64	15.05	0.1089	587.76
	128	15.26	0.1008	1059.90
	<i>Mean ± Std.</i>	14.85 ± 0.27	0.1222 ± 0.0142	-

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